

HEAT SPREAD EQUATION .

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ANNOTATION.

In the article The correctness of the generalized solutions of direct and inverse problems to the heat equation is studied.

Key words : Continuity, functional row, Fure coefficient, tor vibration equation .

ANNOTATION.

The dissertation "Non local boundary conditional direct and inverse problems in an unbounded domain fot the heat propagation in three-dimensional space" is one of the important sections of mathematics. Interest in this field is determined by the theoretical significance of the obtained results and their practical applications.

Mathematician of physics very many p issues private derivative equations in the form of description can _ Such in description to him suitable was _ borderline issues the solution natural determination opportunity there is and that's it with together , them to solve known methods apply can _ In nature occurring processes fraction in order equations more precisely expression is enough

Heat spread equation .

Koshi issue : In the plain $\Omega = \{(x,t) : 0 < x < l, 0 < t < T\}$ in the field one sexual

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = a^2 \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} \quad (a = \text{const})(1)$$

heat spread of Eq

$$u(x,0) = \varphi(x), \quad 0 \leq x \leq l \quad (2)$$

initial and

$$u(0,t) = 0, \quad u(l,t) = 0, \quad 0 \leq t < T \quad (3)$$

one sexual borderline conditions satisfactory regular the solution be found

Definition : (1) of Eq regular or classic as Ω a solution in the domain , in Eq participant his own derivatives with continuously and the equation to the point spinning $u=u(x,y)$ to the function it is said .

A mix issue variables split (or Fourier) method with we solve . To this method essentially (1) of Eq the solution

$$u(x,t) = X(x)T(t) \quad (4)$$

in the form if we look for the following

$$X''(x) + \lambda X(x) = 0, (5)$$

$$T'(x) + a^2 \lambda T(t) = 0 (6)$$

two simple differential equation harvest will be , in this $\lambda = \text{const.}$ (4) expression and (3) marginal from conditions Equation (5). for the following

$$X(0) = X(l) = 0 (7)$$

borderline conditions come comes out

Problem (5), (7) is a characteristic number and special functions to find about Sturm-Liouville issue is a narrow vibration equation for mixed issue also built in solution was _

this matter special numbers $\lambda_n = \left(\frac{\pi n}{l}\right)^2, (n = 1, 2, \dots)$, this special to the thighs

correspondingly non- trivial special functions $X_n(x) = \sin \frac{\pi n}{l} x$ in appearance

that determined we λ were = λ_n of equation (6) when common the solution

$$T_n(t) = a_n e^{-(a\pi n/l)^2 t}$$

to look have is , according to equality (1.2.4)

$$U_n(x,t) = X_n(x)T_n(t) = a_n e^{-\left(\frac{\pi na}{l}\right)^2 t} \sin \frac{\pi n}{l} x$$

functions (a_n - optional , immutable numbers) equation (1). and (3) marginal condition satisfies . Eq one sexual that it was for this solutions sum again solution will be That's why (2), (3) of equation (1) for conditions satisfactory the solution

$$u(x,t) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a_n e^{-\left(\frac{\pi na}{l}\right)^2 t} \sin \frac{\pi n}{l} x \quad (8)$$

series in the form of we are looking for If (8) Functional series and his t according to first , x according to second in order derivatives flat approaching if , then boom row the sum of equation (1). and (3) marginal conditions satisfies . Primary if we require that the condition also be satisfied ,

$$u(x,0) = \varphi(x) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a_n \sin \frac{\pi n}{l} x$$

to equality have we will be This equality $\varphi(x)$ of the function (0, λ) in the interval sinuses according to Fure to the line spread if we say , in that case a_n Fure coefficient being _

$$a_n = \frac{2}{l} \int_0^l \varphi(x) \sin \frac{\pi n}{l} x dx \quad (9)$$

according to the formula is found .

(9) to Eq mainly solution (8) of problem (1)-(3). the following in appearance to write possible

$$u(x,t) = \int_0^l G(x,y,t) \varphi(y) dy, \quad (10)$$

this on the ground

$$G(x,y,t) = \frac{2}{l} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} e^{-\left(\frac{\pi n a}{l}\right)^2 t} \sin \frac{\pi n}{l} x \sin \frac{\pi n}{l} y.$$

This is a function instant of the source effect function is called

1- Theorem. If $[0, l]$ is on the cross section $\varphi(x)$ function

1. continuous ;
2. to piecemeal-continuous h o sila have and
3. $\varphi(0) = \varphi(l) = 0$

condition satisfies , then row (8). mixed of the matter $\bar{\Omega}$ continuous at and infinite differentiable the solution will be

(2) function mixed of the matter the solution to be for , (2) initial provided given $\varphi(x)$ function continuous , fragmented smooth and initial and borderline of conditions adaptation provided ($\varphi(0) = \varphi(l) = 0$) submission need _ But $\varphi(x)$ of the function continuity and adaptation condition satisfaction practice for heavy is a must .

For example , $U_0 = const$ up to temp heated and on the edges zero to the temperature have was , cooled in the stern heat spread in the case of , initial and borderline of conditions adaptation condition is not performed , ie $\varphi(0) = \varphi(l) = 0 = U_0 \neq 0$. In this case the following theorem is appropriate .

2- Theorem. If $[0, l]$ is on the cross section $\varphi(x)$ function piece-continuous (I - to type breaks has) , then function (10) :

- 1) $\Omega(1)$ of the equation the solution will be
- 2) $\bar{\Omega} = \{(x,t) : 0 \leq x \leq l, 0 \leq t \leq T\}$ in the field limited ;
- 3) (3) marginal conditions satisfies ;
- 4) at $t=0$ $\varphi(x)$ of the function continuously at the points continuously and $u(x, 0) = \varphi(x)$.

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